

BI-LATERAL COMPARISON OF V-BAND ANTENNA GAIN BETWEEN KRISS AND NIST

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Abstract

A bi-lateral comparison of power gain for a V-band (50 GHz – 75 GHz) Cassegrain antenna and a standard horn antenna has been performed between KRISS and NIST. This paper describes the comparison and its progress so far. Measurement results will be presented at the conference.

Introduction

So far, two international comparisons of gain for horn antennas, i.e., Key Comparison at Ka-band (CEM.RF-K3.F (GT-RF 92-1)) and International Comparison at X-band (GT-RF 78-5), have been carried out below 40 GHz. The purpose of these comparisons was to evaluate consistency between participating NMIs (National Metrology Institutes) in gain measurements for horn antennas.

Operating frequency ranges used in areas of satellite broadcasting/communications and local area wireless communications are rapidly becoming broader and higher. In addition, the use of high gain antennas has become more popular. For these reasons, it is of interest to compare gain for a high gain antenna as well as a horn antenna between NMIs in the millimeter-wave frequency range higher than 40 GHz.

A bi-lateral comparison of V-band antenna gain has been performed between KRISS and NIST. This paper describes the comparison and its progress so far.

Description of the Comparison

For this comparison, the traveling standards consist of a Cassegrain type high gain antenna (Antenna #1) and an electro-formed standard horn antenna (Antenna #2), as shown in Table I. Antenna #1 is selected to compare consistency between the two participants in near-field antenna measurements used for characterizing high-gain antennas, while Antenna #2 is selected to compare consistency in the three-antenna extrapolation range measurements used for characterizing standard gain horn antennas and near-field probes used in near-field antenna measurements.

Measurement parameters for this comparison are the power gain and complex reflection coefficient of the traveling standards, where measurement uncertainty budget for the coverage factor $k = 1$ is required for only power gain. The maximum gain for the Antenna #1 is requested at 65 GHz while the boresight gain for the Antenna #2 is requested at 50 GHz, 65 GHz, and 75 GHz, where the boresight direction is defined as the normal to the antenna aperture. The complex reflection coefficient of the antennas is measured at the same frequencies as the gain measurement.

Table I Specifications of traveling standards

Identification	Antenna #1	Antenna #2
Type	Cassegrain	Standard gain horn
Dimension	8 inch (D)	38 mm (W) 29 mm (H) 71 mm (L)
Nominal gain	40 dBi	23 dBi
Frequency range	65 GHz	50 GHz – 75 GHz
Polarization	Linear	Linear
VSWR	< 1.15	< 1.1
Connector	WR-15	WR-15

Measurement System and Technique

1. KRISS

Measurements are performed on a planar near-field antenna measurement system with an operating frequency range of 2 GHz to 110 GHz, as shown in Figure 1, where it consists of a planar near-field scanner, a microwave subsystem and an extrapolation range.

The transmitting part of the microwave subsystem is based on an external mixer configuration and is modified to form a reflectometer for measuring the impedance of the transmitting/receiving antennas, the generator and load without using the vector network analyzer in the millimeter-wave frequency range [1]. The power gain of the high-gain antenna is determined by taking the Fourier transform of the complex near field that was measured using the planar near-field measurement system [2]. The

standard horn antenna and near-field probe used in the near-field antenna measurements are characterized by using a three-antenna extrapolation technique [3].

Figure 1. V-band planar near-field range at KRISS.

2. NIST

The gain of the horn Antenna #2 was determined at 50 GHz, 65 GHz and 75 GHz using a three-antenna extrapolation method [3]. These measurements were performed on the NIST millimeter-wave extrapolation range, as shown in Figure 2.

The horn Antenna #2 was used as the near-field probe in measuring the gain of the Cassegrain Antenna #1. These near-field measurements were performed at 65 GHz on the NIST 2.5 m x 2.5 m planar near-field range, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. NIST millimeter-wave extrapolation range with standard gain horn under test on the right.

Figure 3. NIST millimeter-wave planar near-field range with dish under test to left (before alignment).

Progress of the Comparison

According to the agreed protocol, the comparison has been performed between KRISS and NIST. The measurements at NIST were completed in May 2007 and the measurements at KRISS are expected to complete in March 2008.

Details of the bi-lateral comparison and measurement results and uncertainties will be presented at the conference.

References

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